

Filter substrate comparison and biodegradable flocculant dosing for a compact constructed wetland treating combined sewer overflow

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Compact CSO—CW tested with various filter substrates at small-scale.
- Biopolymer dosing enhanced particle and COD retention.
- Nutrient removal was unaffected by biopolymer dosing.
- Sorptive materials like zeolite and activated carbon improved pollutant removal.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Combined sewer overflows (CSO) are a significant source of urban water pollution, with sediments originating from sewers contributing substantial loads of organic matter, nutrients, and particulate-associated contaminants to receiving waters. In Germany, constructed wetlands for CSO treatment (CSO—CWs) are well-established, yet their large surface area limits their implementation in urban areas. The present study investigates the potential of compact CSO—CWs, operated at doubled flow rate, with tailored filter substrates and the addition of biopolymers to enhance treatment performance. A series of flocculation experiments was first conducted to identify a suitable biopolymer for CSO treatment. Subsequently, small-scale pilot column tests were performed to evaluate compact CSO—CW configurations. Here, different filter substrates were investigated, including sand, sand-gravel, gravel, shells, sand-activated carbon, and sand-zeolite, with and without the selected biopolymer introduced into the inflow to assess its effect on treatment performance. Results show that compact CSO—CWs with suitable substrates and increased flow rates achieved removal efficiencies comparable to the reference CSO—CW in standard operation, exhibiting only minor deviations. Sorptive and fine-grained substrates (activated carbon, zeolite) demonstrated high performance for particulates, COD, DOC, and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, respectively. Biopolymer dosing significantly enhanced particle and COD retention in coarse filter substrates (gravel, shells), thereby reducing performance differences across configurations. In contrast, phosphorus removal remained limited across all configurations, independent of biopolymer dosing. These findings demonstrate that compact CSO—CWs can provide a robust treatment option for CSOs and urban runoff under increased hydraulic loading, particularly in densely populated areas.

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Glossary

DN	Nominal diameter
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
CSO	Combined sewer overflow spills
CSO—CW	Constructed wetlands for combined sewer overflow
IQR	Inter-quartile range
LOQ	Limit of quantification
NH ₄ —N	Ammonium-Nitrogen
o-PO ₄ -P	orthophosphate
P _{tot}	Total phosphorus
RSF	Retention Soil Filter
TOC	Total organic carbon
TSS	Total suspended solids
TSS ₆₃	Total suspended solids < 63 μm
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

1. Introduction

Despite major advancements in surface water treatment following the implementation of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive and the Water Framework Directive, urban pollution persists as a significant contributing factor to surface water quality issues throughout the European Union. Approximately 60 % of European surface waters are still classified as being in poor biological and chemical status. One of the main reasons for this is urban runoff containing pollutants from combined and separate sewer systems (Cojoc et al., 2024; EEA, 2018). Combined sewer overflow spills (CSOs) and stormwater discharges transport a complex mixture of particulate, particulate-bound, or dissolved pollutants, including nutrients, organic matter, heavy metals, and a wide range of organic micropollutants, such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, pesticides, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (Becouze-Lareure et al., 2019; Gasperi et al., 2012; Montes-Grajales et al., 2017; Müller et al., 2020; Mutzner et al., 2022; Zgheib et al., 2012).

These complex pollutant profiles, coupled with increased frequency of storm events resulting from climate change, underscore the necessity for advanced treatment strategies to mitigate their impact on aquatic environments effectively, especially in densely populated areas (Wu et al., 2024). For 30 years in Germany, retention soil filters (RSFs) have served as effective instruments to improve quality before CSOs or stormwater enter the receiving environment by retention, buffering, and natural treatment (Uhl and Dittmer, 2005). Internationally, RSFs can be classified as vertical flow constructed wetlands (CWs), specifically

designed for CSO and stormwater treatment (Meyer et al., 2013; Rizzo et al., 2020; Tondera, 2019). In the present study, the term CSO—CW will be referred to in the context of RSF.

Studies keep consistently demonstrating the efficiency of CSO—CWs in managing CSO and stormwater treatment by targeting nutrients, oxygen-depleting substances, total suspended solids, heavy metals, pathogens, and selected micropollutants (Christoffels and Mertens, 2014; Cross et al., 2021; Frechen, 2013; Grotehusmann et al., 2015; Pálffy et al., 2017; Ruppelt et al., 2020a; Tondera et al., 2013a, 2019). The treatment performance within CSO—CWs is influenced by its specific design and operational parameters, such as filter substrate composition, biofilm development, residence time, and the development of a biological active secondary surface layer (Dittmer, 2006; Dittmer et al., 2016; Frechen, 2010; Tondera, 2019), as well as catchment characteristics, pollutant loads, and the dynamics of storm events (Rizzo et al., 2020). In the context of German RSF practice, CSO—CWs are operated intermittently and are designed to fully drain after each loading event in order to establish aerobic conditions within the filter substrate and enable nitrification processes during dry periods (Dittmer et al., 2016; Tondera, 2019). A cross-section and the elements characteristic of CSO—CWs are presented in Fig. 1.

Hydraulic operation represents a fundamental design parameter which affects both treatment performance and space requirements. The discharge rate is throttled and related to the CSO—CW's surface area. In a separated sewer system, the CSO—CW can operate at higher maximum flow rates (0.01–0.05 L s⁻¹ m⁻²) compared to combined sewer systems (0.01–0.03 L s⁻¹ m⁻²), as there are usually lower pollutant loads (Grotehusmann et al., 2015). Consequently, increasing the area-related hydraulic loading rate is a primary mechanism for reducing the required CSO—CW surface area. However, this approach simultaneously shortens residence times and challenges established removal mechanisms.

Despite their demonstrated effectiveness in removing high pollutant concentrations and their low maintenance requirements, the widespread application of CSO—CWs is constrained by their substantial space requirements. Design guidelines generally recommend a CSO—CW surface area of approximately 1 % of the connected impervious catchment area (DWA, 2019; Grotehusmann et al., 2015), which limits their application in spatially constrained urban environments.

To address this limitation, investigations in the StopUP research project aimed to develop a more compact CSO—CW to reduce the required surface area by increasing the area-related hydraulic loading while maintaining treatment performance. However, hydraulic intensification reduces residence time within the filter substrate, thereby reducing treatment performance. One promising strategy to counteract

Fig. 1. Structure, elements, and cross-section of a CSO—CW (modified according to DWA (2019) and Grotehusmann et al. (2015)).

this limitation could be the integration of biodegradable flocculants (biopolymers) into the inflow of CSO—CWs to enhance the aggregation of fine suspended particles into larger flocs (Bratby, 2016; Nyström et al., 2020). Fine particles are of particular concern in the context of CSOs, as they are characterised by a high specific surface area and a strong potential to bind pollutants such as heavy metals and organic contaminants which pose a high risk to aquatic ecosystems (Baum et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2022).

To date, only a limited number of studies have investigated flocculation for the treatment of urban runoff. Nyström et al. (2019) demonstrated that flocculation significantly enhanced the removal of turbidity, total suspended solids (TSS) and heavy metals from road runoff compared to sedimentation. In a subsequent study, reductions of up to 90 % in organic parameters such as total organic carbon (TOC) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons were reported following chitosan-based biopolymer application (Nyström et al., 2020). El Samrani et al. (2008) reported the general suitability of flocculation for CSO treatment, but also highlighted the strong dependency of treatment efficiency on flocculant dosage and influent variability (El Samrani et al., 2008).

In contrast, the integration of biopolymers into CWs has received minimal attention. To the best of the authors' knowledge, one study has investigated the combination of biopolymers with CWs, focusing on wastewater from small batik industries rather than CSOs (Rahmadyanti and Febriyanti, 2020). A systematic evaluation of flocculation as a process intensification strategy for compact CSO—CWs, particularly under the intermittent loading and drainage conditions characteristic of RSFs in Germany, is currently lacking.

Against this background, the present study investigates a compact CSO—CW concept that combines two complementary approaches to process intensification: firstly, investigating alternative filter substrates with properties distinct from sand for effective CSO treatment; secondly, enhancing treatment performance through the introduction of biopolymers into the CSO—CW influent to improve removal efficiency under increased hydraulic loading. Using small-scale pilot columns operated at twice the hydraulic loading rate, the study assesses how reduced residence times and varying substrate properties affect the CSO—CW treatment performance and whether potential performance losses can be compensated for by biopolymer dosing. The present study aims to contribute to the development of space-efficient and robust nature-based solutions for CSO treatment in urban environments with spatial constraints.

2. Materials and methods

All experiments were conducted at the μ^3 Research Centre of the ISA, which is located at the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) Aachen-Soers, Germany. To eliminate weather influences, an experimental wastewater similar to CSO was required for both the flocculation and the small-scale pilot column tests. The experimental CSO used for flocculation tests was prepared by adjusting the wastewater from the primary clarification tank to a target typical CSO turbidity range of 30–70 NTU (Storath et al., 2024) and diluting it with wastewater from WWTP effluent in cases of higher initial turbidity values. Since parameters beyond turbidity are relevant for characterising CSO, target water quality parameters for the small-scale pilot column tests were defined from the literature for pH (6.5–7.5), chemical oxygen demand (COD) (80–100 mg L⁻¹), ammonium nitrogen (NH₄-N) (4–6 mg L⁻¹), and total suspended solids (TSS) (90–120 mg L⁻¹) (Supplementary material, Table S.3). Previous studies indicated that the desired composition was obtained using 20 % primary clarifier effluent and 80 % WWTP effluent under dry-weather conditions (Ruppelt et al., 2020a) and 25 % primary clarifier effluent and 75 % WWTP effluent under wet-weather conditions (Linnemann et al., 2024).

2.1. Preliminary investigations of biodegradable flocculation agents

In this study, 16 commercially available biopolymers based on chitosan and potato starch (Supplementary material, Table S.1) were investigated for their suitability in treating CSO through lab-scale jar tests. A two-phase experimental approach was chosen: Simplified initial pre-screening, followed by detailed optimisation of operating parameters (optimal concentrations and mixing conditions) of selected biopolymers. Jar tests were performed following the standardised methods by ASTM D2035-13 (D19 Committee, 2019), evaluating turbidity reduction (WTW, Turb 355 T/IR) as a key performance indicator. A stock solution of 0.1 wt.-% was prepared for all purchased biopolymers. Chitosan-based biopolymers were dissolved in a 1 wt.-% acetic acid solution, whereas starch-based biopolymers were dissolved in ultra-pure water (MERCK MILLI-Q IQ 7000).

Pre-screening experiments were conducted using a standardised jar test procedure with a multiple stirrer system (Lovibond ET 750). Each biopolymer was added at varying concentrations (1, 10, 25, 50, and 100 mg L⁻¹) into 500 mL of experimental CSO. Initially, a homogenization phase was performed at 200 rpm for 30 s to ensure uniform dispersion of the flocculants. Subsequently, a flocculation phase followed at 50 rpm for 5 min, facilitating the growth of larger flocs. Finally, a sedimentation phase was conducted for 60 min to allow the separation of the clarified supernatant from the settled flocs. The maximal turbidity decrease of each of the 16 pre-screened biopolymers was determined by comparing the initial turbidity prior to flocculant addition with the turbidity of the supernatant after the sedimentation phase.

Following the evaluation of pre-screening experiments, more comprehensive jar test series were performed with a selection of three promising biopolymers. The tests were carried out under identical conditions as described in the pre-screening phase. The goal was to optimize the parameters: biopolymer concentration, mixing speed, and mixing duration. Concentration experiments were repeated to confirm the optimal concentration for each selected biopolymer. Subsequently, further tests were conducted at these identified optimal concentrations to examine the effects of varying mixing speeds (20–80 rpm) and mixing durations (1–9 min) during the flocculation phase. All experimental conditions were replicated twice to ensure reproducibility. The evaluation was again based on the maximal turbidity decrease achieved.

2.2. Small-scale pilot column tests

2.2.1. Experimental design

Fourteen small-scale pilot columns (DN 150) were constructed to evaluate six filter substrate configurations, each tested as replicate, both without and with dosing of a biopolymer. Columns were built in accordance with the Retention Soil Filter Manual for Planning, Construction, and Operation of the federal state of North Rhine-Westphalia, Germany (Grotehusmann et al., 2015). Each column comprised a 15 cm drainage layer of gravel (2/8 mm) and a 70 cm thick filter substrate and was planted with one plant of *Phragmites australis* (Supplementary material, Fig. S.1 and Fig. S.2). The filter substrates investigated are given in Table 1. Columns 1 and 2 served as a reference operated without biopolymer addition to represent the typical CSO—CW set-up (designed after (Grotehusmann et al., 2015)) at a hydraulic loading rate of 0.05 L s⁻¹ m⁻². Columns 3–14 were operated at an elevated loading rate of 0.10 L s⁻¹ m⁻², thereby simulating a CSO—CW with half the surface area required to treat the same CSO discharge. Columns 3 and 4 were designed as a direct counterpart to the reference configuration, but with doubled hydraulic loading, enabling an isolated assessment of flow rate effects. Columns 5 and 6 contained a sand-gravel-mix as a filter substrate, while columns 7 and 8 were filled exclusively with gravel. Columns 9 and 10 contained a mix of sand and activated carbon, reflecting the design of the first full-scale RSF^{plus} implementation in Rheinbach, Germany. (Brunsch et al., 2019, 2020). Columns 11 and 12 were filled with shells (AA Minerals Type D) and

Table 1

Investigated filter substrates and experimental design in the small-scale pilot columns. C=column.

Column	Filter substrate	Identifier	Grain size mm	Flow rate $L s^{-1} m^{-2}$
C1/2	Sand	S1	0/2	0.05
C3/4	Sand	S2	0/2	0.1
C5/6	Sand/Gravel (50/50 wt.- %)	SGR	0/8	0.1
C7/8	Gravel	GR	2/8	0.1
C9/10	Sand/Activated Carbon (0–10 cm: 80/20 wt.- % 10–50 cm: 100/0 wt.- % 50–70 cm: 60/40 wt.- %)	SAC	0/2.5	0.1
C11/12	Urban Rainshell: AA Minerals Type D	AAMin.	0/25	0.1
C13/14	Sand/Zeolite (0–10 cm: 80/20 wt.- % 10–50 cm: 100/0 wt.- % 50–70 cm: 60/40 wt.- %)	SZ	0/2.5	0.1

columns 13 and 14 with a sand-zeolite-mix, applying the same weight ratio of zeolite as activated carbon in the RSF^{plus} configuration. A comprehensive overview and supplementary key indicators (e.g. grain size, bulk density), are presented for the individual substrates in Table S.2.

2.2.2. Sampling and analysis

Prior to the start of sampling, all columns were flushed with approximately 100 L of WWTP effluent without a specific flow rate to remove remaining fine material from the substrates. To mimic a combined sewer influent, an experimental CSO was prepared as reported by (Linnemann et al., 2024; Ruppelt et al., 2020a). The experimental campaign comprised two phases. In the first phase (January 2024 - January 2025), 54 loadings were conducted, resulting in a cumulative hydraulic filter load of $34 m^3 m^{-2}$ and an operational equivalent of approximately 26 months (calculated with an average hydraulic filter load of $16 m^3 m^{-2} a^{-1}$) (Linnemann et al., 2024). Ten of these 54 loadings were sampled and analysed.

In the second phase (February 2025 - March 2025), a further five loadings were applied, of which three were sampled. In contrast to phase I, Heppix OT (biopolymer) at $5 mg L^{-1}$ active substance concentration was dosed to the inflow of columns 3–14. Following jar-test results, the biopolymer was mixed for one minute with a portable mortar mixer ($\sim 650 rpm$) into the intermediate bulk container where the experimental CSO was prepared, and subsequently subjected to 5 min of slow mixing (26 rpm) to ensure complete flocculation. The columns were then loaded with the experimental wastewater. By the end of phase II, the cumulative hydraulic filter load amounted to $37.2 m^3 m^{-2}$, corresponding to approximately 28 months of in situ operation.

After homogenisation of the experimental CSO, influent grab samples of 2 L were taken. For effluent sampling, the initial 500 mL was discarded to adjust the flow rate. The remaining effluent volume ($\sim 10.8 L$) was collected in its entirety, homogenised and a 2 L subsample was taken for laboratory analysis. Thus, each event was sampled approximately 4.0 h for C1/2 and 2.0 h for C3–14. The sampling procedure was performed identically for phases I and II.

To compare the treatment performance of the different filter substrates TSS, fine particles $\leq 0.063 mm$ (TSS₆₃), turbidity, COD, total organic carbon (TOC), dissolved organic carbon (DOC), NH₄-N, total phosphorus (P_{tot}), and orthophosphate (o-PO₄-P) were analysed. The methods used for the analyses of different parameters are summarized in Table S.4(Supplementary material).

Median concentrations for each configuration investigated were calculated according to the mean concentration of the respective column pair. Treatment performances based on median concentrations were calculated. If a value was below the limit of quantification (LOQ), half of

the LOQ was assumed for further calculations (Keizer et al., 2015).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Biopolymers for CSO treatment

3.1.1. Pre-screening experiments

Pre-screening experiments demonstrated that chitosan-based biopolymers exhibited superior turbidity reduction capabilities, with Heppix WS, Heppix T, and Heppix OT achieving turbidity reductions of approximately 87.7 %, 86.4 %, and 85.3 %, respectively. Among starch-based products, PolySepar SK72 displayed the highest performance at approximately 64.9 %. Other starch-based products demonstrated no significant turbidity reduction. The control samples, however, showed an average turbidity reduction of 33.1 % (Supplementary material, Fig. S.2). Heppix WS, Heppix OT, and one starch-based biopolymer, PolySepar SK72, were selected for the subsequent comprehensive jar test series.

3.1.2. Optimal concentration determination

The detailed jar tests for optimal dosage showed distinct optimal concentrations for each selected biopolymer: $8 mg L^{-1}$ for Heppix WS, $5 mg L^{-1}$ for Heppix OT, and $150 mg L^{-1}$ for PolySepar SK72. Heppix WS confirmed its superior efficacy, maintaining consistently high turbidity removal. Heppix OT showed a smaller optimal concentration range with a peak reduction of 76.4 %, indicating dosage sensitivity (Supplementary material, Fig. S.3). PolySepar SK72 provided steady but comparatively lower turbidity removal ($\sim 50 %$) across a broader dosage range, suggesting its performance is reliable yet requires higher dosages.

3.1.3. Influence of mixing speed and duration

Increasing mixing speeds during the flocculation phase improved turbidity removal across all three biopolymers, indicating enhanced particle collision and floc formation at higher mixer speeds up to 80 rpm (Supplementary material, Fig. S.4). Overall, no floc fragmentation was observed, suggesting potential for higher degrees of turbulence without compromising floc stability (Bubakova et al., 2013; Pivokonský et al., 2022).

Extending the flocculation duration from one to nine minutes significantly improved turbidity reduction across all investigated biopolymers. However, beyond 5 min, only a negligible $\sim 5 %$ increase in turbidity reductions was observed (Supplementary material, Fig. S.4). The observed plateau in turbidity reduction beyond a flocculation time of approximately 5 min indicates that the dominant aggregation mechanisms, including charge neutralisation and polymer bridging, are largely completed within short contact times. Prolonged mixing provides only limited additional benefit, likely due to saturation of available binding sites and the establishment of a dynamic equilibrium between floc growth and restructuring (Bratby, 2016). Prolonged flocculation periods may further result in a decreased removal efficiency due to elevated levels of flocs undergoing breakage (Getahun et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2022). Practical implementation suggests a flocculation duration of approximately five minutes to balance effectiveness and infrastructural requirements in full-scale CSO—CWs applications (channel length).

3.2. Small-scale pilot column tests

The inflow concentrations that represent the target water quality for the experimental CSO, as achieved in the small-scale pilot column tests, are summarised in Table S.3 (Supplementary material). All target values were met, with the exception for TSS, which remained below the defined target concentration. An increased TSS concentration would have necessitated the addition of higher proportions of primary clarifier effluent. This would have resulted in elevated COD and NH₄-N concentrations, which are not representative of typical CSO compositions.

For this reason, the TSS deviation was accepted in the present study.

3.2.1. Particles and turbidity

3.2.1.1. Total suspended solids (TSS). TSS and TSS₆₃ concentrations, as well as turbidity measurements, are demonstrated in Fig. 2a), b), and c).

Fig. 2. a) TSS, b) TSS₆₃, c) Turbidity, d) COD, e) TOC and f) DOC in the inflow and effluent of the small-scale pilot columns in the first (without biopolymer dosing) and in the second (with biopolymer dosing) phase. *n* = number of samples.

In the first experimental phase, the influent TSS concentration was 30.0 mg L⁻¹. The lowest effluent concentrations were achieved in the reference RSF C1/2 (3.1 mg L⁻¹) and the sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 (4.7 mg L⁻¹), resulting in removal efficiencies of 90 % and 85 %, respectively. Sand C3/4 (5.6 mg L⁻¹; 81 %) and sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (5.8 mg L⁻¹; 81 %) showed similar performance. Higher TSS effluent concentrations were identified for sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (7.6 mg L⁻¹; 75 %), gravel C7/8 (11.0 mg L⁻¹; 65 %), and shells C11/12 (13.0 mg L⁻¹; 58 %), reflecting the lower particle retention of coarser substrates.

Within the second experimental phase, when the biopolymer was dosed, the influent TSS concentration was 42.0 mg/L. Despite the increased load, TSS removal improved in most configurations. The highest performance was observed in sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (4.5 mg L⁻¹; 89 %), sand C3/4 (4.8 mg L⁻¹; 89 %), and sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (5.3 mg L⁻¹; 87 %), with sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 also remaining high (6.3 mg L⁻¹; 85 %). Coarse materials such as gravel C7/8 (8.2 mg L⁻¹; 80 %) and shells C11/12 (11.0 mg L⁻¹; 74 %) still performed less effectively but clearly benefited from biopolymer addition. For coarse substrates, there was a marked improvement in treatment performance after the addition of biopolymers, whereas finer substrates achieved high removal efficiencies, independently of biopolymer dosing. The TSS removal rates observed in this study were consistent with the findings of [Tondera \(2019\)](#), who reported a median removal efficiency of 87 % for TSS in full-scale, established CSO—CWs. In contrast, [Frechen \(2013\)](#) found a TSS removal rate of 96 %, which exceeds the results obtained in this study.

3.2.1.2. Fine fraction of total suspended solids (TSS₆₃). In the first phase, median influent TSS₆₃ was 18.0 mg L⁻¹. The sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 achieved the highest removal (1.6 mg L⁻¹; 91 %), followed by the reference RSF C1/2 (1.9 mg L⁻¹; 89 %). Moderate removals were found in sand C3/4 (4.8 mg L⁻¹; 73 %), sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (5.1 mg L⁻¹; 71 %) and sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (4.2 mg L⁻¹; 76 %), while gravel C7/8 (8.5 mg L⁻¹; 51 %) and shells C11/12 (9.2 mg L⁻¹; 48 %) showed lowest retention.

Following the second phase, influent TSS increased to 33.0 mg L⁻¹, yet the highest removal rates were identified for sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (1.1 mg L⁻¹; 96 %), sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 (2.4 mg L⁻¹; 93 %), and sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (2.5 mg L⁻¹; 92 %). These were in the same range as the reference C1/2 and sand C3/4, which both achieved 92 % removal (2.8 mg L⁻¹). Coarse filter substrates improved significantly to 88 % for gravel C5/6 (4.05 mg L⁻¹) and to 81 % for shells C11/12 (6.2 mg L⁻¹).

3.2.1.3. Turbidity. The influent turbidity was 23.0 NTU in phase I of the experiments. The reference C1/2 (3.6 NTU; 84 %), the sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 (4.4 NTU; 81 %) and sand C3/4 (5.5 NTU; 76 %) achieved highest turbidity removals, while gravel C7/8 (8.1 NTU; 64 %), sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (8.4 NTU; 63 %) and sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (9.1 NTU; 60 %) performed less effectively. The shells C11/12 (11.0 NTU; 53 %) showed the lowest removal, indicating the limitations of coarse substrates in turbidity reduction.

In the second phase, influent turbidity remained similar at 22.0 NTU, but reductions improved in most configurations. Sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 had the highest performance (2.8 NTU; 88 %), followed by sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (3.2 NTU; 86 %) and reference C1/2 (3.7 NTU), as well as sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (3.8 NTU), which both yielded in 83 % turbidity reduction. While coarse filter substrates like gravel C7/8 (4.0 NTU; 82 %) and shells C11/12 (5.2 NTU; 77 %) benefited most from dosing biopolymer into the influent. The only exception was C3/4 (9.0 NTU), which decreased to 59 % removal, likely due to a laboratory measurement error.

3.2.2. Organic matter

3.2.2.1. Chemical oxygen demand (COD). COD, TOC, and DOC concentrations are displayed in [Fig. 2d](#), [e](#), and [f](#)). In these figures, COD and TOC predominantly represent particulate-bound organic matter, whereas DOC reflects the dissolved organic fraction. In the first experimental phase, the influent COD concentration was 51.0 mg L⁻¹. The sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 achieved the highest removal (7.5 mg L⁻¹; 85 %). The removal from sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (19.0 mg L⁻¹; 63 %), sand C3/4 (20.0 mg L⁻¹; 61 %), and sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (23.0 mg L⁻¹; 56 %) was in the same range as the removal of the reference C1/2 (18.0 mg L⁻¹; 65 %). Coarser filter substrates showed significantly lower performance, with shells C11/12 (30.0 mg L⁻¹; 41 %) and gravel C7/8 (31.0 mg L⁻¹; 39 %).

In phase II, COD removals improved across all configurations due to a higher influent concentration of 155.0 mg L⁻¹. The highest removal of 95 % was observed for sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10, resulting in an effluent concentration of 7.5 mg L⁻¹. Sand C3/4, sand-zeolite-mix C13/14, and the reference C1/2 showed a removal of 87 % with an effluent concentration of 20.0 mg L⁻¹ for C3/4 and C13/14, and 21.0 mg L⁻¹ for C1/2. Sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (23.0 mg L⁻¹) and shells C11/12 (26.0 mg L⁻¹) yielded comparable removals of 85 % and 83 %, respectively. Whereas gravel C7/8 (34.0 mg L⁻¹; 78 %) performed less effectively.

The introduction of biopolymers led to a significant enhancement in COD removal in coarse substrates, whilst no additional effect was observed in finer substrates, which had already demonstrated high removal rates. This enhancement suggests that the primary function of the biopolymer application was to improve the retention of particulate-bound organic matter. The effect observed in coarse substrates suggests that flocculation-induced particle aggregation can compensate for retention limitations associated with high permeability and reduced effective contact during infiltration. In contrast, finer substrates already provided high particulate retention without additional flocculation. The findings of this study demonstrate that the COD removal results are consistent with those observed in full-scale CSO—CWs by [Tondera \(2019\)](#), which reported 61 % removal efficiency. However, these results remain below the removal of approximately 80 % documented by [Ruppelt et al. \(2020b\)](#) for pilot CSO—CWs and by [Frechen \(2013\)](#) for a full-scale CSO—CW.

3.2.2.2. Total organic carbon (TOC). In phase I, influent TOC was 17.0 mg L⁻¹. The highest removal of 91 % occurred in sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10, corresponding to an effluent concentration of 1.6 mg L⁻¹. Configurations containing sand as filter substrate showed similar removals with 66 % for reference C1/2 (5.9 mg L⁻¹), 65 % for sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (5.9 mg L⁻¹), sand C3/4 (6.6 mg L⁻¹) and sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (6.6 mg L⁻¹), whereas coarser substrates like gravel C7/8 (12.0 mg L⁻¹; 32 %) and shells C11/12 (8.4 mg L⁻¹; 51 %) showed the lowest TOC retention.

Following the second phase, influent TOC increased to 33.0 mg L⁻¹. Sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 maintained the high removal with 96 % to an effluent concentration of 1.4 mg L⁻¹, followed by sand C3/4 (7.3 mg L⁻¹), sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (7.4 mg L⁻¹) and sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (7.6 mg L⁻¹) with 78 % removal for C3/4, as well as C13/14, and a removal of 77 % for C5/6. Similar removal of 74 % was found for reference C1/2 with an effluent concentration of 8.6 mg L⁻¹. The lowest TOC removals were observed for gravel C7/8 (12.0 mg L⁻¹; 64 %) and shells C11/12 (11.0 mg L⁻¹; 68 %), however, represented an improvement compared to phase I.

The TOC results demonstrated similar trends to those observed for COD. This further supports the interpretation that biopolymer dosing affects the particulate-bound organic fraction. [Tondera \(2019\)](#) showed TOC removal rates ranging from 61–74 %, while [Ruppelt et al. \(2020b\)](#) reported values between 77 % and 80 %. These ranges correspond well with the removal rates identified in the present study, where the

addition of biopolymers to coarse substrates resulted in TOC removal rates comparable to those achieved by standard CSO—CW.

3.2.2.3. Dissolved organic carbon (DOC). For DOC, the influent concentration in the first phase was 15.0 mg L⁻¹. Sand-activated-carbon-mix C7/8 again achieved the highest removal of 92 % with an effluent concentration of 1.2 mg L⁻¹. The reference C1/2 (4.9 mg L⁻¹), sand C3/4 (5.2 mg L⁻¹), sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (5.3 mg L⁻¹), and sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (5.6 mg L⁻¹) showed similar, but moderate removals of 68 %, 66 %, 65 % and 63 %, respectively. Shells C11/12 (6.2 mg L⁻¹; 59 %) and gravel C7/8 (6.5 mg L⁻¹; 57 %) performed less effectively.

With biopolymer dosing (phase II), the DOC concentration in the influent was 23.0 mg L⁻¹. Sand-activated-carbon-mix C7/8 (1.4 mg L⁻¹; 94 %) maintained the highest removal, followed by sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (6.7 mg L⁻¹; 71 %), sand C3/4 (7.2 mg L⁻¹; 69 %), and sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (7.3 mg L⁻¹; 68 %). The removal of reference C1/2 (7.6 mg L⁻¹) and gravel C7/8 (9.8 mg L⁻¹) remained at 67 % and 58 %, respectively, whereas the coarser shells C11/12 (8.2 mg L⁻¹) benefited from biopolymer dosing with an increased removal of 64 % in total.

For DOC removal, biopolymer dosing, appeared to be ineffective. Nevertheless, sand-activated-carbon-mix was the most effective

configuration, as for TOC and COD, reaching removal rates of approximately 90 %, which are comparable to values reported for activated carbon modified CSO—CWs (Brunsch et al., 2018). In contrast, these authors observed a DOC removal of 18–36 % in a conventional CSO—CW. Contrary to this finding, earlier research by Tondera (2019) and Ruppelt et al. (2020b) demonstrated results indicative of DOC removal rates of between 44 % and 60 %. These results are consistent with those observed in the present study for finer substrates.

3.2.3. Nutrients

3.2.3.1. Ammonium nitrogen (NH₄-N). NH₄-N, o-PO₄-P, and P_{tot} concentrations are displayed in Fig. 3a), b), and c). In the absence of biopolymer dosing (phase I), the influent NH₄-N concentration was 2.80 mg L⁻¹. The lowest effluent concentration of 0.05 mg L⁻¹ (LOQ=0.1 mg L⁻¹) was observed for sand-zeolite-mix C13/14, corresponding to a removal of 98 %, followed by reference C1/2 (0.32 mg L⁻¹; 89 %). The sand C3/4 and sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 showed moderate performance with effluent concentrations of 0.69 mg L⁻¹ and 0.74 mg L⁻¹, respectively. This resulted in a removal of 75 % for C3/4 and 74 % for C9/10. The coarser filter substrates sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (1.3 mg L⁻¹; 54

Fig. 3. a) P_{tot}, b) o-PO₄-P, and c) NH₄-N in the inflow and effluent of the small-scale pilot columns in the first (without biopolymer dosing) and in the second (with biopolymer dosing) phase. n = number of samples.

%), shells C11/12 (1.70 mg L⁻¹; 39 %), and gravel C7/8 (1.80 mg L⁻¹; 36 %) performed less effectively.

These results indicate adsorption-based removal processes depending on contact time, resulting in higher effluent concentrations for the finer substrates, which were operated at 0.1 L s m⁻² instead of 0.05 L s m⁻² as the reference C1/2 (Taddeo et al., 2017). For coarser filter substrates, reduced NH₄-N removal efficiencies are further impacted by the lower specific surface area, which limits biofilm establishment and consequently reduces adsorption and biological transformation of NH₄-N (Dittmer, 2006).

The second phase showed a higher influent NH₄-N concentration of 5.70 mg L⁻¹. Despite the higher load, sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 again achieved the highest removal of 99 %, with an effluent concentration of 0.05 mg L⁻¹ (LOQ=0.1 mg L⁻¹). Followed by sand C3/4 and sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10, both of which stayed at a moderate removal of 77 %, but due to the higher influent concentrations during this period, had a higher effluent concentration of 1.30 mg L⁻¹. The reference C1/2 (1.80 mg L⁻¹) and gravel C7/8 (3.95 mg L⁻¹) decreased to 68 % and 31 %, respectively. The coarse filter substrate sand-gravel C5/6 (2.65 mg L⁻¹) stayed moderate at 54 % removal, and shells C11/12 showed an improved removal up to 61 % (2.24 mg L⁻¹), but were both still less effective than the reference C1/2.

NH₄-N removal rates of the finer substrates were independent of biopolymer dosing and remained within the range of 60–86 % reported by Tondera et al. (2013b) and 86–95 % showed by Ruppelt et al. (2020b) and Frechen (2013). Coarse substrates did not reach these levels, whereas only the sand-zeolite-mix exceeded the reported removal efficiencies, confirming the relevance of ion-exchange processes for NH₄-N removal.

3.2.3.2. Orthophosphate (o-PO₄-P). In the first phase, influent o-PO₄-P was 0.27 mg L⁻¹. The highest removal of 81 % occurred in reference C1/2, sand C3/4, and sand-zeolite-mix C13/14, corresponding to effluent concentrations of 0.05 mg L⁻¹ (LOQ=0.1 mg L⁻¹). Sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 (0.08 mg L⁻¹), and shells C11/12 (0.12 mg L⁻¹) showed moderate removal rates with 72 % and 56 %, respectively. Sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (0.20 mg L⁻¹; 28 %) performed less effectively, whereas the o-PO₄-P removal with 7 % in gravel C7/8 (0.25 mg L⁻¹) was negligible.

In phase II, influent o-PO₄-P was 0.40 mg L⁻¹. The removal of o-PO₄-P decreased in all configurations, with shells C11/12 (0.29 mg L⁻¹) showing the highest removal of 43 % and remaining at a moderate level. The reference C1/2 (0.31 mg L⁻¹) decreased to 23 % removal, whereas gravel C7/8 (0.45 mg L⁻¹) showed an o-PO₄-P release of 11 %. Sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (0.29 mg L⁻¹; 29 %), sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 (0.29 mg L⁻¹; 28 %), sand C3/4 (0.30 mg L⁻¹; 25 %), and sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (0.32 mg L⁻¹; 21 %) had similar removals as the reference, indicating that the biopolymer addition had no influence on o-PO₄-P retention, but that CaCO₃ content in filter substrate, such as in shells, can influence o-PO₄-P adsorption as reported as well by Nguyen et al. (2020).

3.2.3.3. Total phosphorus (P_{tot}). The first phase showed a P_{tot} influent concentration of 0.581 mg L⁻¹. Sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 (0.013 mg L⁻¹) (LOQ=0.025 mg L⁻¹) showed the highest removal of 98 %, followed by sand C3/4 (0.079 mg L⁻¹; 86 %), sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (0.154 mg L⁻¹; 74 %) and sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (0.154 mg L⁻¹; 73 %), which all showed higher or similar removal as the reference C1/2 (0.120 mg L⁻¹; 79 %). Coarser substrates such as gravel C7/8 (0.258 mg L⁻¹; 56 %) and shells C11/12 (0.230 mg L⁻¹; 60 %) performed less effectively.

In the second phase, P_{tot} concentration increased to 0.952 mg L⁻¹. P_{tot} results followed the evaluation of o-PO₄-P, as P_{tot} retention in phase II also decreased in most columns. However, sand-activated-carbon-mix C9/10 again showed the highest removal of 78 %, corresponding to an effluent concentration of 0.206 mg L⁻¹, followed by sand C3/4 (0.282 mg L⁻¹; 70 %) and shells C11/12 (0.282 mg L⁻¹; 70 %) as well as the reference

C1/2 (0.292 mg L⁻¹) and sand-zeolite-mix C13/14 (0.298 mg L⁻¹) which both yielded in a 69 % removal. The sand-gravel-mix C5/6 (0.362 mg L⁻¹) and gravel C7/8 (0.459 mg L⁻¹) decreased to 62 % and 52 % removal, respectively.

Ruppelt et al. (2020b) showed o-PO₄-P removal rates of 57–59 %, which are consistent with the findings of the present study. Tondera (2019) determined that P_{tot} removals of approximately 70 % were dependent on filter age and the progressive depletion of sorption sites. In this study, comparable values were achieved by finer substrates and shells under biopolymer dosing, whereas coarse substrates such as sand-gravel and gravel did not reach these removal rates. In contrast, Frechen (2013) documented higher removal rates, with 75 % for o-PO₄-P and 80 % for P_{tot}, which exceed the results observed in this study. This difference can be attributed to the full-scale CSO—CW being amended with iron hydroxides, thereby providing enhanced phosphorus sorption capacity.

3.2.4. Biopolymers for compact CSO—CW: Comparison and interpretation

The difference in removal efficiency between the reference C1/2 and the compact CW columns C3–14 is demonstrated in Fig. 4a) for phase I (without biopolymer dosing) and in Fig. 4b) for phase II (with biopolymer dosing). The columns C1/2 represent the benchmark system, reflecting the typical design and performance of a conventional CSO—CW. The central objective of this study was to minimise the difference of the compact CW columns C3–14, operated at elevated hydraulic loading rates, with varying filter substrates, and with biopolymer dosing in phase II, from this benchmark to evaluate their suitability as space-efficient alternatives. The reference CSO—CW C1/2 exhibited the highest treatment performance for almost all parameters when biopolymer dosing was not applied. The application of biopolymers resulted in a significant enhancement of removal performance across most configurations, thereby leading to a substantial reduction in deviation from the reference CSO—CW, with some configurations exceeding the reference. This highlighting the potential of biopolymer dosing to balance substrate-specific differences and enhance overall treatment efficiency.

3.2.4.1. Particles and turbidity. The results obtained demonstrate that, while finer and sorptive media, such as sand-activated-carbon-mix and sand-zeolite-mix, consistently achieved high particle removal, even in the presence of elevated flow rates, the application of biopolymer resulted in a substantial enhancement in TSS, TSS₆₃, and turbidity removal across most configurations. In particular, the coarser filter substrates exhibited a significant enhancement in removal efficiency, approaching comparable levels as observed for finer and sorptive substrates. These findings emphasise the capacity of flocculation to mitigate the structural limitations of coarse substrates by promoting the aggregation of fines into larger flocs, which filtration processes can more efficiently retain.

Chen et al. (2022) identified that the primary source of CSOs' pollutants was sewer-related sediments, accounting for up to 70 % of the total pollution load. These sediments were found to contain high concentrations of carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus, and PAHs, which are known to be significant contributors to the pollution of surface water bodies. As demonstrated by Rigano et al. (2025), there is considerable mutagenic potential in *C. riparius* when exposed to sediments from an urban runoff sedimentation basin. These findings underscore the necessity of effective particle retention in CSO and urban runoff treatment. In this context, innovative approaches such as compact CSO—CW systems, which demonstrate high particle retention capacity within a reduced footprint, are a promising and sustainable solution, particularly for densely populated areas.

As with all CSO—CWs, the applicability of the concept is inherently linked to a defined range of influent characteristics typical of CSOs, which are commonly characterised by TSS concentrations and particle

Fig. 4. Difference (CX/Y-C1/2) in removal efficiency in a) phase I (without biopolymer dosing) and b) phase II (with biopolymer dosing).

size distributions used for design purposes (e.g. TSS₆₃) in Germany (DWA, 2019; Grotehusmann et al., 2015). Within this framework, the applied methodological approach, combining substrate selection under hydraulic intensification with flocculation, is transferable to other CSO–CW designs and local wastewater conditions. However, it is important to acknowledge, that with elevated hydraulic loading rates and the addition of biopolymers to the inflow, higher particulate retention is expected. While this enhances treatment performance, it also raises the risk of accelerated surface clogging. Consequently, long-term performance, maintenance requirements and potential clogging dynamics must be considered in the design and scaling of compact CSO–CW systems. Long-term investigations are therefore required to assess the extent of clogging under continuous operation. Ji et al. (2022) reported that coarser filter substrates can mitigate clogging, which highlights the importance of substrate selection when considering long-term stability.

3.2.4.2. Organic matter. Clear differences in the removal of organic matter were observed between the particulate-bound and dissolved fractions, which were strongly influenced by the type of substrate. Without biopolymers, the sand-activated carbon mix clearly outperformed all other configurations due to its high sorptive capacity (Brunsch et al., 2018; Knorz et al., 2018). Meanwhile, sand-based filters achieved reductions at a level similar to the reference filters, and coarse substrates such as gravel and shells performed poorly. The results suggest that organic matter removal in finer filter substrates is already high due to their superior filtration performance (Dittmer, 2006). With the addition of biopolymer, COD and TOC retention improved across nearly all substrates; however, finer substrates were only marginally affected. Conversely, the effect of biopolymer was clearly apparent in coarser substrates, where removal efficiency increased substantially to levels comparable to finer substrates. In contrast to the effects of COD and TOC, the DOC removal was only marginally affected by biopolymer dosing. This finding indicates that the applied biopolymer did not interact with dissolved organic matter. Analyses of the influent before and after biopolymer addition showed no relevant increase in DOC or TOC concentrations attributable to the biopolymer, demonstrating that the applied dosages did not introduce a significant additional organic load to the system (Supplementary Material, Table S.5). Only the sand-activated-carbon mix achieved consistently high reductions, while other configurations showed only minor improvements. This highlights the need for sorptive media to target dissolved organics effectively, despite the occurrence of increased flow rates. In summary, biopolymer

dosing effectively strengthens the removal of bulk organic matter and balances performance across different substrates. However, efficient treatment of dissolved organics still requires the use of specifically sorptive material, such as activated carbon, compared to the reference and non-sorptive substrates.

3.2.4.3. Nutrients - NH₄-N. The results suggest improved in NH₄-N retention under compact CSO–CW operation and biopolymer dosing. However, this cannot be explained by direct interactions between the biopolymer and NH₄⁺ ions. As Heppix OT is a cationic biopolymer, it primarily targets negatively charged suspended and colloidal particles (Holmes et al., 2023), and is therefore technically ineffective at binding dissolved and monovalent cationic NH₄⁺ ions (Bratby, 2016).

In conventional CSO–CWs, the NH₄-N removal is predominantly influenced by two processes. The primary mechanism involves the temporary retention of NH₄-N within biofilms developing on the surface of the filter substrates, where NH₄-N is subsequently oxidised during aerated dry phases. In aged systems, an additional contribution arises from ion-exchange processes associated with negatively charged surfaces in the enriched secondary filter layer that accumulates over time (Dittmer et al., 2016; Tondera, 2019).

In the compact CSO–CW systems investigated in Phase I (without biopolymer dosing), substrate-specific effects became apparent. Columns containing zeolite exhibited higher NH₄-N removal than the reference columns (C1/2), indicating that ion-exchange processes at the zeolite surface played a dominant role under reduced residence times (Ji et al., 2022). Conversely, columns containing alternative substrates showed a lower NH₄-N removal in comparison to the reference, indicating that reduced contact times predominantly limited biofilm-mediated NH₄-N retention.

In Phase II (with biopolymer dosing), a significant decrease in NH₄-N removal was observed in the reference columns (approximately 20 %), while NH₄-N removal in the other substrate configurations remained largely constant between Phase I and Phase II. This resulted in a relative improvement of NH₄-N removal in the biopolymer-dosed columns compared to the reference. Moreover, the addition of biopolymer resulted in enhanced particle retention, which may lead to synergistic interactions with ion-exchange processes and biofilm activity on the retained particles and NH₄-N. Consequently, this may be associated with increased NH₄-N retention under compact CSO–CW operation and biopolymer dosing. However, this effect must be observed through a long-term study.

Furthermore, the dynamics of NH₄-N demand additional

investigation. In the context of German CSO—CWs, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ is predominantly oxidised via nitrification during dry periods, thereby preserving the adsorption capacity of sand. In zeolite-based filters, however, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ removal relies mainly on ion-exchange, which gives rise to questions regarding long-term saturation and the possibility of regeneration of exchange sites by nitrification processes.

3.2.4.4. Nutrients - phosphorus. Phosphorus removal showed similar behaviour between the dissolved and particulate fractions. Retention of $\text{o-PO}_4\text{-P}$ was highest in sand-based filters during the first phase, but declined in all configurations over time, indicating the exhaustion of sorption sites (Tondera, 2019). Substrates containing carbonate, such as shells, retained higher levels of phosphate, demonstrating the importance of mineral composition in phosphorus adsorption (Nguyen et al., 2020). Notably, biopolymer dosing had no measurable impact on $\text{o-PO}_4\text{-P}$ removal, emphasising that flocculation is ineffective for controlling dissolved phosphorus and that achieving effective retention requires specific additives, such as iron hydroxides (Ji et al., 2022). In contrast, P_{tot} retention was generally higher than $\text{o-PO}_4\text{-P}$ retention, confirming that particulate phosphorus was removed by filtration across all substrates, but also decreased over time, mirroring the $\text{o-PO}_4\text{-P}$ trend. Overall, P_{tot} effluent concentrations in both phases were approximately at the same level as $\text{o-PO}_4\text{-P}$ effluent concentrations, which shows that particulate-bound phosphorus is retained by filtration of the filter substrates used in this study, even without biopolymer dosing, including the coarser filter substrates. Despite this, in some cases, measured P_{tot} concentrations were below $\text{o-PO}_4\text{-P}$ concentrations. This can be explained by measurement uncertainties or incorrect sample preparation, as differences were only slight.

In addition to substrate-specific sorptive properties, differences in hydraulic retention time between coarse and fine filter substrates need to be considered when interpreting removal efficiency. Although the outflow of the CSO—CW system is hydraulically throttled, resulting in comparable hydraulic retention times during operation, substrate-dependent hydraulic effects occur primarily during the initial infiltration phase of each loading event. During this phase, local flow velocities and effective contact times are determined by grain size, pore structure, and hydraulic conductivity. Subsequently, finer-grained substrates are expected to provide longer effective retention and contact times, favouring particle retention and associated removal processes, such as adsorption. Conversely, coarser filter substrates exhibit higher permeability and shorter effective retention during infiltration. This hydraulic behaviour provides a plausible explanation for the observed performance differences between coarse and fine substrates and for the pronounced effect of biopolymer dosing in coarse substrates. In these cases, flocculation can partially compensate for retention limitations associated with high permeability and reduced retention times during infiltration.

3.2.4.5. Implications for long-term operation and maintenance. The CSO—CW filter substrate is notable for its capacity to function as a biologically active soil matrix rather than a passive adsorption bed. Retained organic particulate matter and adsorbed dissolved organic compounds bound to mineral surfaces are subject to microbial degradation, which, over time, contributes to a partial regeneration of pore space and sorption capacity. In addition, the retention of inorganic compounds, such as $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ and heavy metals, occurs through adsorption, ion-exchange or surface complexation processes. Biofilms have been shown to play a particularly important role in the dynamics of $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ retention, owing to the adsorption of NH_4^+ ions onto biofilms developing on the surfaces of soil particles within the filter substrate. The $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ retained undergoes subsequent biological transformation via nitrification, thereby partially regenerating cation-exchange sites. Conversely, heavy metals may undergo processes such as precipitation or stable surface complexation, which can similarly reduce the

occupancy of exchange sites (Dittmer, 2006; Pinnekamp et al., 2017; Woźniak, 2008). Together, these coupled physico-chemical and biological processes establish a dynamic balance between accumulation, transformation and release within the filter substrate.

Nevertheless, the long-term saturation of sorptive capacities cannot be excluded under sustained or intensified loading conditions. Furthermore, the enhanced particle aggregation and retention resulting from biopolymer dosing may accelerate solids accumulation within the pore structure or the filter surface, thereby increasing the risk of clogging, particularly in compact systems operated at elevated hydraulic loading rates. Such effects may influence maintenance intervals, for example by necessitating surface layer renewal or partial substrate replacement. It should be noted that the increased particulate retention resulting from biopolymer application may indirectly influence microbial community structure and associated carbon and nitrogen transformation pathways (Daims, 2005). While such effects were not investigated in the present study, they represent an important aspect for future research aimed at optimising long-term treatment efficiency and stability of compact CSO—CWs.

From an operational perspective, the application of biopolymer dosing introduces additional technical components compared to conventional CSO—CW systems, which typically operate without electrical or mechanical devices. Full-scale implementation therefore requires dosing and storage infrastructure for the biopolymer, associated control and monitoring units, and regular inspection. This may increase operational complexity and maintenance effort relative to a passive CSO—CW. These aspects do not negate the advantages of compact CSO—CWs but highlight that intensified treatment concepts require careful consideration of long-term operation, maintenance strategies, and system robustness during design and upscaling.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that compact CSO—CW systems with a halved filtration area can achieve removal rates comparable to those of conventional CSO—CWs. When substrate selection is tailored to target parameters, compact CSO—CW configurations operated at doubled hydraulic loading achieve treatment performances with only minor deviations from conventional CSO—CWs, whereas biopolymer dosing can effectively compensate for retention limitations associated with coarse substrates.

Sorptive and fine-grained materials inherently sustain high retention of particulates and organic matter, whereas the addition of biopolymers is particularly effective in enhancing particle retention in coarse filter substrates, thereby compensating for retention limitations under intensified hydraulic loading across all configurations.

The results confirm that biopolymer application primarily supports particulate and particulate-bound pollutant removal. In contrast, the removal of dissolved substances, such as DOC, $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$, and $\text{o-PO}_4\text{-P}$, was primarily influenced by sorptive and ion-exchange properties of the substrates, specifically activated carbon and zeolite. This highlights the necessity of sorptive substrates for dissolved pollutant removal. Overall, the findings of this study highlight that the combination of appropriate substrate selection and operational measures establishes compact CSO—CWs as a sustainable option for CSO and stormwater treatment, particularly under spatial constraints in urban environments.

Elevated surface loadings may enhance clogging processes, particularly when fine or highly sorptive filter materials are used. It is recommended that future research focus on extended operation under intensified hydraulic loading conditions and on assessing system performance across a broader range of CSO wastewater compositions to further support full-scale implementation. Furthermore the long-term effects of biopolymer dosing, including the risk of accelerated surface clogging and pollutant release, should be evaluated. In addition, the promising small-scale pilot results must be confirmed in a scaled-up pilot system to establish reliable design parameters for full-scale application.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT / OpenAI to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Julia Storath: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maximilian P. Born:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Frank Benstoem:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Thomas Wintgens:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

I have shared the link to my data at the attach files tep.

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